

MAKING THE LEARNING OF VOCABULARY MORE INTERESTING AND REWARDING

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6628450>

The common sense perspective of how languages are learnt, according to non-language specialists, is that you swap the words in your first language for the corresponding ones in the second language. Words are the foundation upon which a second language's knowledge can be developed. Non-specialists would be astonished if they studied the history of language teaching with this common sense yet naive perspective. Vocabulary has, on the whole, had a rather low reputation in the last 50 years, far from being recognized as crucial to language development. For many years, vocabulary was considered an afterthought to the primary goal of language instruction, which was the development of grammatical understanding of the language. Vocabulary was essential for pupils to have something to grab on to when learning structures, but it was rarely a primary emphasis for learning. Linguists have recently been focusing more on vocabulary, emphasizing its relevance in language training and reevaluating some of the ways in which it is taught and learned.

People are becoming increasingly conscious that learning vocabulary is just as vital as learning grammar, despite the fact that the two are plainly connected. If the skeleton of a language is made up of language structures, the vocabulary is made up of the flesh and essential organs. The understanding of words and their meanings is referred to as vocabulary. "Vocabulary knowledge is knowledge," writes Steven Stahl (2005), "knowledge of a word not only implies a definition, but also suggests how that word fits into the world." Vocabulary knowledge is something that can never be entirely grasped; it evolves and deepens over time. Vocabulary instruction entails much more than looking up words in a dictionary and using them in a sentence. Vocabulary is learned inadvertently through indirect word exposure and consciously through explicit training in specific terms and word learning procedures. The ability to manipulate linguistic structures has no potential for communicating meaning unless words are used. Here, we discuss the necessity of carefully picking one's words. In real life, where vocabulary is employed correctly, it may be able to compensate for grammatical errors. The importance of studying language structures is self-evident, because grammatical knowledge enables us to construct correct sentences. At the same time, we must have meanings that we intend to express,

as well as a vocabulary of words from which to choose when expressing these ideas.

A major issue in vocabulary instruction is that, while there is agreement on what levels grammatical structures should be taught, we can't say the same for vocabulary instruction. There are word lists on certain syllabuses, but there is no assurance that the list for one group of students will be the same as the list for another group of students at the same level. However, we may say that pupils must learn how to use the verb 'to be' before they can learn how to use it as an auxiliary in the Present Continuous Tense. One of the difficulties in teaching vocabulary is deciding which words to teach. Upper intermediate dictionaries frequently contain up to 55,000 words or even more, and a single word might have multiple meanings. They only make up a small portion of a language's total number of words. It takes several years of hard work for a second-language speaker to reach the level of a native speaker. At the very least, the active vocabulary would have to be doubled. According to some linguists, educated native speakers may have an active vocabulary of 8,000 to 10,000 words. A good second-language speaker might have a 3,500-word active vocabulary. That's a significant difference. A general principle of vocabulary selection has been frequency.

The frequency with which specific words are used can assist us in determining which terms we should teach. The words that are most often used should be taught first. Coverage is another principle that has been applied to the vocabulary selection. If a word has multiple meanings, it is more commonly used than if it simply has one. We can browse lists of the most frequently used terms in a language to figure out which words are the most frequently used. Of course, that is the computer's benefit: you can type in a term and it will quickly provide instances of where the word appears in sentences and phrases, as well as how frequently it is used. The Internet offers a near-ideal learning environment. As a result, it should be able to create vocabulary courses based on computerized data. We will be able to make reliable statements about what words to teach if we feed in enough text from newspapers, magazines, books, letters, chats, and so on. There is no doubt that the use of computers has benefited greatly from the knowledge that has been made available to them. However, even with such scientific strength at our disposal, the problem of selection remains unsolved.

The first thing to keep in mind concerning language is that it frequently has several meanings. According to the Concise Oxford Dictionary, "a set of printed papers connected together inside a cover, as a thing to be read," a "book" is "a

group of printed papers attached together inside a cover, as a thing to be read." However, the same dictionary goes on to provide eight more noun meanings, two more verb meanings, and three phrasal verb meanings for "book." As a result, we'll have to say that the term "book" refers to a type of reading material, but it can also refer to a variety of other things. How a term is used can change, stretch, or limit its meaning, and this is something students should be aware of. Metaphor and idiom are commonly used to expand the meaning of words. The meaning of words is also influenced by collocation, or the pairing of words. Words, on the other hand, can change their shape and grammatical value. Students must understand the basics of word creation as well as how to twist words to meet various grammatical situations. They must also understand how suffixes and prefixes function. How can we get the meanings of the phrases forceful and pricey to be diametrically opposed? Why do we use -im for one and -in for the other? Students must also understand how words are spelled and pronounced. Indeed, if pupils are able to grasp words and utilize words in speech, the way words are emphasized – and how that stress might change when their grammatical function is different – as with nouns and verbs, for example – is critical. Learning a word's written and spoken forms is an important part of the process.

As a result, we can conclude that teaching vocabulary entails much more than simply presenting new terms. Of course, this has its place, but there are also some other issues to discuss. For example, throughout one week, kids are exposed to a large number of words, some of which are immediately utilized and others which are not. The following is the query: Should we teach some words that we need for structure practice, but not others that arise inadvertently in reading texts, for instance? Is there any way to motivate students to learn a term for real?

Experiments on vocabulary appear to show that pupils recall the terms best when they have really done something with them. Getting students to do more than just repeat them has a distinct advantage. Tasks such as modifying them to mean the opposite, turning a noun to an adjective, placing words together, and so on enable learners to remember the terms. We must get pupils to interact with language in some way. We should encourage children to "adopt" terms that they enjoy and desire to use. We should encourage children to do things with words so that they can grow familiar with them. Discovery tactics, which require students to figure out rules and meanings for themselves rather than being told everything by the teacher, are a good alternative to traditional presenting

techniques, especially at intermediate and higher levels. This is especially true in vocabulary classes, where students are frequently required to figure out what a term means and why and how it is used.

We can presume that pupils at intermediate levels already have a large vocabulary bank. Rather than teaching kids new words, we can show them instances of terms in texts and encourage them to utilize their prior knowledge to figure out what words go with what, when to use them, and what implications they have. Students can employ discovery approaches with vocabulary items to activate their prior knowledge and share what they know (if they are working with others). "...engaging the learner... is crucial to any activity that is to have a high learning yield," says Adrian Underhill, summarizing the discussion on active and passive vocabulary and interacting.

We've already mentioned how difficult it is to choose words for educational reasons. This was based on the large amount of words found in any language. Students, on the other hand, will almost likely desire to expand their vocabulary beyond what we, their teachers, can teach them. What are their options for obtaining this information? Dictionaries are unquestionably one of the best resources for students who want to expand their vocabulary or, at the very least, comprehend what a term means when they come across it in a text or a discussion. To identify the equivalent in their own language, most students will reference a bilingual dictionary. There is nothing wrong with such dictionaries other the fact that they usually do not provide enough information for pupils to use. A excellent monolingual dictionary is perhaps the most valuable resource we can provide to our kids. They contain details about a term's sound, spelling, word construction, metaphorical and idiomatic usage — its full profile. However, students' lack of usage of monolingual dictionaries is due to more than only linguistic difficulties. Because they include so much technical information, dictionaries can seem intimidating. Unless pupils are taught how to comprehend information and use dictionaries, the money they spend on them will be mostly squandered because they will never use them.

The majority of vocabulary is acquired inadvertently through indirect exposure to words, according to scientific study on vocabulary instruction. Students can pick up vocabulary on their own by having rich oral-language experiences at home and at school, listening to books read aloud to them, and reading widely. In terms of long-term vocabulary growth, reading volume is critical. Extensive reading exposes kids to terms repeatedly or multiple times, and it is also one of the ways pupils see language in context.

It's almost hard to overestimate the power of words; they've truly changed the course of history and will continue to do so. A big, rich vocabulary, as well as the abilities to use those words, is one of the most important tools we can teach pupils for success in school and in life. Our language abilities and word knowledge have an impact on our ability to function in today's complicated social and economic world. A broad vocabulary is more explicitly predictive and reflective of high levels of reading achievement, in addition to the critical relevance of vocabulary for life success.

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